

Artificial Light at Night in the Arctic as Proxy for Industrial Activity and its Relation to Fire Occurrence and Vegetation Changes

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Abstract: Arctic is warming up to four times faster compared to the global average, which leads to major changes in ecosystem processes. This warming also facilitates easier access to the region for economic activity. However the development of industrial activity and its impact on ecological processes is not quantified at pan-Arctic scale. We developed a spatially explicit proxy for industrial activity based on artificial light at night (ALAN) that conventional economics-based methods (e.g., GDP) cannot capture. We found 5.1% of the Arctic was impacted by light-emitting human activity from 1992 to 2013. 85% of the lit area did not contain human settlement, hence can be attributed to industrialization. The hotspots of human activity were in oil and gas extraction regions. This spatially explicit ALAN-based method enabled us to connect industrial economy with ecological processes such as fire occurrence and vegetation changes. Our results show a 2.5 times higher fire occurrence in area lit by human activity compared to control points randomly selected from areas with similar climate conditions. However, the case studies analyzed indicated that fire management practices might reduce fire occurrence in the Arctic. Regarding vegetation changes, we found that mean greenness and annual vegetation change trends are significantly different in lit areas compared to controls however the type of light-emitting human activity further influences the direction of the greenness and trends. Overall, our results indicate human activity functions as a feedback mechanism to climate change in the Arctic.

Keywords: arctic; artificial lights at night; industrial activity; vegetation changes; fire occurrence.

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